

BIOCHEMISTRY AND GENETICS OF ANIMALS

GROWTH, HEALTH STATUS AND COST BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF WEANER PIGS FED DIET SUPPLEMENTED WITH MALTODEXTRIN

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Abstract

This study evaluated the influence of maltodextrin in the diet of weaned pigs on growth, backfat thickness, haematology, serum biochemical and cost benefit indices. A total of 54 weaned pigs which are largewhite × landrace crosses with average weight of 9.35 ± 2.36 kg were used for this study. They were randomly allotted to three dietary treatments (T1 - basal diet, T2 - 500g/tonne maltodextrin inclusion, T3 - 1kg/tonne maltodextrin inclusion) with three replicates each and six animals per replicate in a completely randomized design. The body weight gains of the pigs were not significantly ($P > 0.05$) affected by the dietary treatments. They were 23.65, 25.92 and 24.63 kg in T1, T2 and T3 respectively. At the 6th week of the study, the FCR was significant ($P < 0.05$) and were 3.62, 4.26 and 3.81 in T1, T2 and T3 respectively. However, the FCR at the 13th week was not significant ($P > 0.05$) among the treatments. The high density lipoprotein cholesterol were significantly higher in T2 (56.33 mg/dL) and T3 (52.00 mg/dL) than in T1 (46.00 mg/dL). The back fat thickness and all the haematological indices measured were not significantly ($P > 0.05$) influenced by the dietary treatment. The feed cost per weight gain improved with inclusion of maltodextrin from ₦1,213.03 in T1 to ₦1,153.77 in T2 and ₦1,120.75 in T3. The supplementation of maltodextrin in the diet of weaned pigs did not negatively influence the growth and the health status of the animals.

Keywords: Health Status, Maltodextrin, Postweaning performance, Feed utilization, Blood profile.

Introduction

Weaning is one of the most critical stages in pig's life because of the need to adjust to dietary and environmental changes. These changes could have adverse effect on the intestinal and immune systems resulting in impaired health and growth particularly during the first few weeks post-weaning. At weaning, the sows' milk is replaced by a dry and less digestible starch-based diet (Williams, 2003), resulting in significantly reduced energy intake for epithelial structure maintenance (Pluske *et al.*, 1996), reduced transmucosal resistance (Spreeuwenberg *et al.*, 2001, Boudry *et al.*, 2004), and increased secretory activity in the small intestine (Boudry *et al.*, 2004). With the underdeveloped innate and adaptive immune systems of the weaned pigs, damage to the epithelial layers also reduces the ability of nutrients to be digested and absorbed into the blood stream which increases the substrates available for pathogen proliferation (Pluske *et al.*, 2002). These biological changes have short and long-term effects on subsequent performance of pig in terms of growth and well being. As a result of this, it is important that swine producers use appropriate health, nutrition, and management strategies to minimize the adverse effects of weaning stress so as to improve productivity.

A nutritional strategy to promote an early feed consumption after weaning is the use of highly palatable and digestible ingredients in the post-weaning diet,

such as milk-derived products, or highly digestible cereal or animal origin protein sources (Solà-Oriol *et al.*, 2009). Apart from the main ingredients, non-nutritive feed additives, such as zinc oxide, acidifier, flavour and antibiotics are often incorporated to stimulate gut health and digestive capacity (Heo *et al.*, 2013). Hence, the need for an alternative non-conventional feed additive. Due to the adaptive nature of piglet's digestive system to milk components, post weaning diets have been formulated with lactose-rich ingredient that stimulate the intake of feed, help diet transitions (Berrocoso *et al.*, 2012), and increase nutrient digestibility (O'Doherty *et al.*, 2005), thereby mitigating the decrease in post weaning performance. Studies by Mahan and Newton (1993) and Oliver *et al.* (2002) have shown that it is possible to use hydrolyzed corn starch (Maltodextrin) as replacement for lactose in diets of infants without adversely affecting performance.

Notably, one of the main sources of energy for an infant's development and growth comes from carbohydrates. Maltodextrins (MDs) are a class of carbohydrates (CHOs) industrially produced by enzymatic or acid hydrolysis of the starch, followed by purification and spray drying (Takeiti *et al.*, 2010). It has an energy value of approximately 4 kcal/g (Katouzian *et al.*, 2015). Studies have shown that maltose and maltodextrin are digested by a set of enzymes called maltases. These enzymes are responsible for about 70 and 20% of the hydrolysis of those carbohydrates, respectively.

Maltodextrin has the ability to lower the pH of the contents of the rectal cavity and has been implicated in lowering the total coliform and *E. coli* populations in the caecum thus, having a prebiotic effect (Pivetta *et al.*, 2014). Also, it has been reported to be effective in partially or totally (Augusto *et al.*, 2011; Pivetta *et al.*, 2014) substituting lactose in the feed of weaned piglets. Lactase activity has been reported to be lower than maltase activity in weaner pigs (Kidder, 1980), hence, maltodextrin supplementation in the diet of weaner pigs might induce the synthesis of maltase through the modulation of enzyme activity exerted by the substrate with improved performance. This study assessed the influence of supplementing the diet of weaned pigs with varying level of maltodextrin on the performance, back fat thickness, cost benefit and health status of the animals in a tropical environment.

Materials and methods

This study was carried out at AK Research Farms, Eleyele, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria with daily temperature ranging between 25 - 35°C and annual rainfall of 1800mm (Victory *et al.*, 2022). The study lasted 91 days. Fifty-four weaned piglets (large white x landrace crosses) with mean weight of 9.35±2.36kg (±SE) were used for the experiment. They were administered 0.2 - 0.3 mg/kg of ivermectin injection sub-cutaneously against internal and external parasites before the commencement of the experiment.

The animals were housed in open sided cross ventilated pens with concrete floor under good management practices. The pens were equipped with concrete water trough and Big Dutchman's semi-automatic feeder. Water and Feed were supplied *ad libitum* throughout the experimental period. Daily routine practices carried out included feeding, watering, waste disposal, washing of pens and general observation of the animal's welfare.

The pigs were randomly allotted into 3 dietary treatments labeled T1, T2 and T3 in a completely randomized design (CRD). Each treatment was replicated 3 times with 6 animals per replicate. The diet of T1 (control/basal diet) was formulated to meet the nutrients requirements as recommended by the National Research Council (2012) for weaned pigs raised in tropical environment (Table 1). Pigs in T2 were fed basal diet with 500g/tonne maltodextrin while T3 contained the basal diet with an inclusion rate of 1kg/tonne maltodextrin.

The feed intake was estimated daily by subtracting the weight of the left over feed from that of the feed given. The body weight of the pigs were determined weekly using a walk-through digital measuring scale. The weight gain was calculated as the difference between the initial weight and the final weight. The feed conversion ratio (FCR) was determined as the ratio of feed intake to weight gain.

Table 1

Percentage Composition of Basal Diet	
Ingredients	Quantity %
Maize	40.00
Groundnut cake	25.00
Wheat offal	10.00
Corn bran	16.00
Fish meal	2.50
Limestone	2.00
Bone meal	2.00
Lysine	0.40
Methionine	0.325
Salt	0.40
Starter Premix	0.25
Toxin binder	0.05
Multi enzyme	0.05
Lavaricide	0.025
Palm oil	1.00
Total	100
Calculated Composition	
Metabolizable energy (Kcal/kg)	2650
Crude fiber (%)	5.73
Crude protein (%)	19.67

The proximate composition of the samples of the three diet were determined using the recommended procedures described by Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 2010). The backfat thickness were measured across the treatment at the 12th week of the study using the ultrasonic probe technique described by Fortin *et al.* (1980) and modified by Jiang *et al.* (2014). The ultrasonic probe technique works on the principle of reflection of sound wave. The calibration of the instrument was based on the assumption that the ultrasonic sound waves travels through fatty tissue at a

velocity of 1480 m/s. The backfat thickness was taken off the midline over the last rib using ultrasound gel on the probe. This was done using the Dramiski ultrasound scanner.

At the end of the feeding trial, pigs were randomly selected from each treatment and sampled for blood through the jugular vein into clinical sample bottles for analysis using hypodermic syringe and needle. The blood sampled for serum biochemistry analysis were collected into sterile plain sample bottles without anti-coagulant while those for haematological analysis were

sampled into bottles with anti-coagulant (EDTA) to prevent the blood from clotting. The sampling was done in the morning before feeding. About 5mls of blood samples were collected from each animal and were stored in iced flask till it was delivered to the laboratory some minutes after collection. The blood sampled for haematology were analysed for packed cell volume (PCV), haemoglobin concentration, erythrocyte count, leucocyte count, platelets, lymphocytes, neutrophils, monocytes, eosinophils, mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC), mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCH) and mean cell volume (MCV). For serum biochemical analysis, the sampled blood

were centrifuged for 20 - 30 min at 4000 rpm to separate the serum from the cells. The serum was analysed for total protein, albumin, aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine amino transferase (ALT), blood urea nitrogen, creatinine, glucose, total cholesterol, high density lipoprotein cholesterol and triglyceride. The globulin, albumin-globulin ratio (A:G) and low density lipoprotein cholesterol were estimated.

Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) procedures using the General Linear Model procedures of SAS (2002). The means among variables that were significant were separated using the Duncan's Multiple Range (DMR) Test.

Table 2

Proximate Composition of Experimental Diet			
SAMPLE	T1	T2	T3
Crude Protein (%)	19.43	19.625	19.835
Ether Extract (%)	3.79	3.865	3.825
Crude Fibre (%)	3.595	3.555	3.52
Ash (%)	5.59	5.46	5.345
Moisture (%)	11.355	11.19	11.135
Gross Energy (Kcal/g)	4.0215	4.031	4.0395
Nitrogen free extract (%)	67.595	67.495	67.475

Results and Discussion

The performance of weaned pig fed different levels of maltodextrin till week 6 is as highlighted in Table 3. At week 6 no significant difference was observed in the body weight, feed intake and weight gain among the treatments. The weight gain were 8.68, 7.24 and 7.75 kg in T1, T2 and T3 respectively at week 6. However, the feed conversion ratio (FCR) significantly differs among the treatments. The group fed with diet containing 500g/tonne maltodextrin (T2) had the significantly ($P<0.05$) highest FCR (4.26) but was not significantly ($P>0.05$) different from group fed with 1kg/tonne maltodextrin, T3 (3.81). The FCR of T2 however, differ significantly ($P<0.05$) from that of T1 fed the control diet (3.62). The FCR of T1 and T3 were however not significantly ($P>0.05$) different. At the 13th week of the study, the result obtained is as indicated in Table 4 showed that the feeding of varying levels of maltodextrin to weaned pigs in this study did not significantly ($P>0.05$) influence all the growth indices measured. The final weights were 33.15, 35.20 and 33.89 kg in T1, T2 and T3 respectively. The average daily feed intake ranged from 1.11 kg in the group fed control diet (T1) and 1.21 kg in T2 fed 0.05 % maltodextrin inclusion in the diet. Pigs in T2 had the highest (4.23) feed conversion ratio (FCR), while the lowest was (4.11) recorded

in the group fed 0.1% maltodextrin inclusion (T3). This corroborates the findings of Hauptli *et al.* (2016) who reported no significant effect of feeding weaner pigs with maltodextrin. Pivetta *et al.* (2014) also reported that the inclusion of maltodextrin on the diet of weaned pigs did not compromise the performance of the pigs but depressed feed intake. The significant difference seen between the FCR of T1 and T2 at week 6 may suggest that feeding maltodextrin may only be useful for a short period postweaning. The reports of O'Doherty *et al.* (2010) and Kim *et al.*, (2010) suggest that maltodextrin improve the performance of weaned pigs from first week of inclusion and was identified to have similar effects with lactose. However, there may be need to ascertain the effect of feeding maltodextrin for longer periods on the performance of the pigs. The thickness of back fat in weaner pig is related to growth and reproductive indices (Roongsitthichai and Tummaruk, 2014). The backfat thickness of pigs fed varying levels of maltodextrin the diet is as shown in Figure 1. The backfat thickness of the weaner pigs were not significantly influence by the inclusion of maltodextrin in the diet. They were 8.50, 10.25 and 9.75 mm in T1, T2 and T3 respectively.

Table 3

Performance of Weaned Piglets Fed Different Levels of Maltodextrin at Week 6				
PARAMETERS	T1	T2	T3	SEM
Initial Weight (kg)	9.50	9.28	9.26	0.91
Final Weight (kg)	18.17	16.52	17.0	1.76
Weight Gain (kg)	8.68	7.24	7.75	0.91
Average Daily Gain (g)	206.60	172.36	184.47	21.6
Feed Intake (kg)	30.83	30.88	29.15	2.94
Average Daily Feed Intake (g)	734.10	735.23	721.16	69.97
Feed conversion Ratio	3.62 ^b	4.26 ^a	3.81 ^{ab}	0.10

^{a, b} Means with different superscript across the row are significantly different at $\alpha=0.05$

T1 - Control (Without maltodextrin)

T2 - 500g/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

T3 - 1kg/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

Table 4

Performance of Weaned Piglets Fed Different Levels of Maltodextrin at Week 13				
PARAMETERS	T1	T2	T3	SEM
Initial Weight (kg)	9.50	9.28	9.26	0.91
Final Weight (kg)	33.15	35.20	33.89	2.07
Weight Gain (kg)	23.65	25.30	24.63	1.29
Average Daily Gain (g)	0.26	0.28	0.27	0.02
Feed Intake (kg)	101.20	109.73	102.46	7.63
Average Daily Feed Intake (Kg)	1.11	1.21	1.13	0.08
Feed conversion Ratio	4.20	4.23	4.11	0.17

T1 - Control (Without maltodextrin)
T2 - 500g/tonne maltodextrin inclusion
T3 - 1kg/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

Fig 1: Back fat thickness (mm) of weaner pigs fed varying levels of maltodextrin in the diet.

Haematological and serum biochemical assays play crucial roles in assessing the physiological and health status of animals (Adenkola *et al.*, 2009; Etim, 2014; Koomkrong *et al.*, 2017). The haematology indices of weaner pigs fed varying levels of maltodextrin is as presented in Table 5. No significant ($P>0.05$) effect of the dietary treatments were seen on the haematological indices measured in this study. Similarly, Pivetta *et al.* (2014) that fed maltodextrin at inclusion rate above those in this study reported no significant interaction between diet with maltodextrin and that of fructooligosaccharides for all the haematological parameters measured. Although not significantly ($P>0.05$) notable, maltodextrin had lowering effect on the levels of haematological parameters measured in this study. The packed cell volume (PCV) was 38.00 % in the animals on the control diet (T1), 33.00 % in animals fed 0.5kg/tonne maltodextrin in the diet (T2) while those fed 1kg/tonne maltodextrin in the diet (T3) had 35.33

%. Haemoglobin ranged from 10.67 to 12.40 g/dL in T2 and T1 respectively. The erythrocyte count also referred to as red blood cell (RBC) were 6.05, 5.23 and 5.80 μL in T1, T2 and T3 respectively. The eosinophils were 4.67, 3.33 and 2.33 % in T1, T2 and T3 respectively. Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC) reduced from 32.64 g/dL in T1 to 32.32 g/dL in T2 and 31.90 g/dL in T3. Similarly, Mean haemoglobin concentration (MCH) reduced from 20.83 pg in T1 to 20.39 pg in T2 and 19.47 pg in T3. The reducing effect of maltodextrin on the haematological indices especially the packed cell volume, haemoglobin and red blood cells calls for a monitoring in the use of maltodextrin as a reduction below certain levels will suggest anaemia in the piglets. The values obtained for all the haematological indices in this study fall within the normal physiological range of a weaner pig (Merck Manual, 2012).

Table 5

Haematological parameters of weaner pigs fed varying levels of maltodextrin				
Parameters	T1	T2	T3	SEM
Packed cell volume (%)	38.00	33.00	35.33	35.44
Haemoglobin (g/dL)	12.40	10.67	11.27	11.44
Erythrocytes Count (μ L)	6.05	5.23	5.80	5.69
Total Leucocytes (μ L)	4400.00	4433.33	4300.00	4377.78
Platelets (μ L)	169666.67	116333.33	103333.33	129777.78
Lymphocytes (%)	49.33	48.33	49.33	49.00
Neutrophils (%)	46.33	45.00	45.33	45.56
Monocytes (%)	3.00	3.33	2.33	2.89
Eosinophil (%)	4.67	3.33	4.33	4.11
MCHC (g/dL)	32.64	32.32	31.90	32.29
MCH (pg)	20.83	20.39	19.47	20.23
Mean cell volume (fL)	63.82	61.02	62.65	62.65

T1 - Control (Without maltodextrin)

T2 - 500g/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

T3 - 1kg/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

MCHC - Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration

MCH - Mean corpuscular haemoglobin

The serum biochemicals are important biomarkers which could be suggestive of the impact of external factors such as plane of nutrition on the functionality of tissues, organs and body systems as a whole (Adenkola *et al.*, 2009; Koomkrong *et al.*, 2017). The serum biochemical indices of piglets fed diet containing different inclusion levels of maltodextrin is highlighted in Table 6. The varying inclusion levels of maltodextrin in the diets presented to weaner pigs in this study did not significantly influence the serum biochemical indices assayed in this study except the High density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol. HDL was significantly ($P < 0.05$) highest (56.33mg/dL) in T2 fed diet containing 500g/tonne maltodextrin and different from 46.00 and 52.00 mg/dL recorded in T1 and T3 respectively. The level of HDL in the serum increased with inclusion of maltodextrin in this study. The maltodextrin had a hypolipidemic effect (Hassan *et al.*, 2014) on the pigs. This corroborate the report of Inglett and Grisamore (1991) who stated that the inclusion of maltodextrin in the diet has the potential to reduce bad fat (LDL) and increase good fat (HDL). This is made possible by the action of the beta-glucan component of maltodextrin which lowers total blood cholesterol by improving the HDL and lowering the LDL cholesterol (Inglett and Grisamore, 1991). This is beneficial to the health of the pig. The total protein were 7.00, 7.20 and 7.40 g/dl in T1, T2 and T3 respectively. The Alanine aminotransferase increased from 38.97 IU/l in T1 to 39.67 IU/l in

T2 and 40.50 IU/l in T3. The creatine was 0.77mg/dL in T1 and 0.80 mg/dL in both T2 and T3.

Feed cost takes a very huge proportion of the variable cost of production in most livestock enterprises, that is why farmers are always on the look out for cheaper and effective alternatives. Maltodextrin has been identified as cheaper alternative to other expensive carbohydrate sources especially in the diet of weaner pigs (Machado and Carvalho, 2015). The cost-benefit analysis of maltodextrin supplementation in the diet of weaner pigs is as presented in Table 7. The result showed no significant effect ($P > 0.05$) of maltodextrin supplementation on overall cost of feeding. The average cost of feed consumed per day were ₦270.63, ₦293.72 and 274.51 in T1, T2 and T3 respectively. The feed cost per weight gain decreased across the treatments with increasing level of maltodextrin in the diet. Feed cost per weight gain were ₦1,213.03 in diet fed 0 % maltodextrin (T1), ₦1,153.77 in T2 fed 0.05 % maltodextrin and ₦1,120.75 in T3 fed 0.1 % maltodextrin. The cost per weight gain which was estimated to be higher for the control diet (T1) than in the diets supplemented with maltodextrin (T2 and T3) implies that the cost of including maltodextrin in the diet of pigs is beneficial considering that less is spent on feeding to produce a kg of live weight. This is an indication that the inclusion of maltodextrin diet is beneficial cost and health wise.

Table 6

Serum Biochemical Parameters of Weaners Fed Varying Levels of Maltodextrin				
Parameters	T1	T2	T3	SEM
Total protein (g/dL)	7.00	7.20	7.40	0.11
Albumin (g/dL)	2.90	3.07	3.25	0.06
Globulin (g/dL)	4.10	4.13	4.15	0.06
RATIO	0.71	0.74	0.78	0.01
AST (IU/l)	44.00	47.00	47.00	2.58
ALT (IU/l)	38.67	39.67	40.50	1.95
Blood urea nitrogen (mg/dL)	8.43	8.83	8.80	0.12
Creatinine (mg/dL)	0.77	0.80	0.80	0.01
Glucose (mg/dL)	78.33	82.00	84.50	1.52
Total cholesterol (mg/dL)	91.00	93.67	96.50	1.78
High density lipoprotein (mg/dl)	46.00 ^c	56.33 ^a	52.00 ^b	1.14
Triglyceride (mg/dL)	79.00	84.00	81.50	0.87
Low density lipoprotein (mg/dL)	29.20	20.53	28.20	1.57

^{a, b, c} Means with different superscript across the row are significantly different at $\alpha=0.05$

T1 - Control (without maltodextrin)

T2 - 500g/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

T3 - 1kg/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

AST - Aspartate transaminase

ALT - Alanine aminotransferase

Table 7

Cost-Benefit Analysis of Maltodextrin Supplementation in Diet of Weaner Pigs				
Parameters	T1	T2	T3	SEM
Cost of feed per kg (₦/Kg)	243.36	243.58	243.8	0.06
Total cost of feeding (₦)	24626.95	24626.96	24980.82	1857.51
Average Daily Feed Intake (Kg)	1.11	1.21	1.13	0.08
Average cost of feed/day (₦)	270.63	293.72	274.51	20.41
Feed conversion Ratio	4.20	4.23	4.11	0.17
Feed Cost/Weight Gain (₦/Kg)	1021.30	1029.53	1001.75	40.82

T1 - Control (Without maltodextrin)

T2 - 500g/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

T3 - 1kg/tonne maltodextrin inclusion

Dollar to Naira- \$1 = ₦403

Conclusion

The inclusion of maltodextrin in the diet of weaned pigs did not negatively influence the growth, back fat thickness and health status of the pigs. Maltodextrin had a hypolipidism effect on the pigs by increasing the high density lipoprotein (HDL) and reducing the low density (LDL). Its inclusion also improved the cost per weight of the gain of the pigs. Thus, maltodextrin can be added up to 0.1% in the diet of pigs in the tropics.

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